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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Confidential Computing
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CoCo	Confidential Containers
CNCF	Cloud Native Computing Foundation
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
HIDS	Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
LLM	Large Language Model
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection Systems
PoC	Proof of Concept
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SMS	Secrets Management System
SPA	Single-Page Application
SSO	Single Sign-On
TEE	Trusted Execution Environments
TRE	Trusted Research Environments
UI	User Interface
UISAV	Ústav informatiky SAV
UX	User eXperience
VM	Virtual Machine

1. INTRODUCTION

The SIESTA project aims to enhance the EOSC ecosystem by developing secure, cloud-based tools and services for providing access to and enabling reusability of sensitive personal data, while adhering to FAIR principles, balancing usability for researchers with privacy of data owners.

In this document, we present the release of the first iteration of the SIESTA project platform.

We start with the presentation of the high level service architecture, which includes a description of the different personas involved in the platform, their roles and the interactions they have with the different services. We also provide relationships and how the other projects involved in the same domains can share terminology and commonalities, particularly the possible integrations with the EOSC-EU node.

We then provide implementation details of the different services that constitute the architecture. Moreover, we describe the various technical problems and shortcomings of such an ambitious project. Confidential computing is at the bleeding edge for many of the involved technologies, often necessitating the exploration and integration of emerging solutions that are still evolving and not yet fully production-ready. This, combined with the variety of hardware and the fact that the provider sites are all already at the production status, have brought a number of challenges to implement confidential computing. Testing new software versions is difficult to schedule and sometimes not feasible due to potential service disruptions. Implementing new services on the other hand is less invasive and easier to do.

Next, the current service usage from the use case are briefly summarized (the full details will be provided in the upcoming Technical Report)

The different provider sites (CSIC / IFCA, CNRS / IPHC, IISAS / UISAV) are then presented. They have explored and implemented, in a complementary way, diverse parts of the SIESTA platform, depending on their priorities and technical skill availability. For example, IFCA was focusing on containers whereas IPHC and UISAV were focusing on virtual machines. And then the knowledge about one topic is being shared to the sites that were focused on other subjects, to help advance the platform as a whole.

The different use cases chosen to define the requirements for the platform have diverse needs that should be fulfilled. In WP8, we will examine how this has been achieved and what will need to be improved for the next iteration. A questionnaire to get relevant feedback from the use cases is in preparation.

The first iteration of the SIESTA platform has identified that further technical work is needed in some areas, to increase its applicability for some use cases needs, or to make

the platform easier to use for people with diverse technical backgrounds. This is discussed in the final conclusions.

2. HIGH LEVEL SERVICE ARCHITECTURE & COMMON PERSONAS

2.1. INTRODUCTION

In order to help with understanding the different concepts on which the SIESTA architecture is based on and the way the involved technology stacks are implemented, we introduce high-level notions that are abstracted from the deep technical details, those are described in-depth in later chapters.

We also study the synergies and common terminology that are used within other projects in the same domain, such as EOSC ENTRUST [\[EOEN\]](#) and TITAN [\[TITA\]](#).

2.2. SIESTA PERSONAS

During the initial stages of the platform definition, the need for distinguishing the roles of the different stakeholders arose and, we found that the following three personas were the minimum needed to properly separate the rights and responsibilities related to the security constraints:

1. Data rights holder.
2. Data user.
3. SIESTA platform operator.

These personas represent roles within the platform, and each persona may be composed of **multiple** people sharing that role's responsibilities and permissions.

The **data rights holder** persona is composed of people or organizations responsible for the datasets. They decide under which conditions these datasets can be shared, with whom, and they are responsible for authorizing the data transfers in and out of the SIESTA platform. It is also the responsibility of the data rights holder to organize the dataset according to scientific domain relevant data and metadata standards. Those are formalized frameworks used for organizing and describing data in a consistent and machine-readable manner, and to facilitate data sharing and research reproducibility. As the most sensitive role within the platform, it entails some responsibilities that need some technical competencies. The use case will have to provide those competencies or delegate certain tasks (in a way that respects the involved laws) to people with those competencies.

The **data user** persona represents scientists, researchers that aim to answer a specific research question using the data and tools that are made available for analysis on the SIESTA platform. For some use cases, they are also the developers of part of the tools used in the analysis to answer the scientific question.

The **SIESTA platform operator** persona aggregates all personnel involved in operating the cloud systems that provide infrastructure as a service, as well as platform managed application services. The persona is responsible for managing the underlying hardware and software resources at the provider site level, that encompasses storage, operating system and network administrators and more generally anyone that has any access (physical or software) to the underlying computing platforms or data centers. At the same time, this personnel is responsible for configuring platform-managed application services—such as Secure DataLake, Code Repository, and others—that form an integral part of the data user persona’s toolchain.

More use-case-specific details and explanations about those personas can be found in each work package documentation:

- Use case 1: Epidemiology (WP14) [\[UC1\]](#)
- Use case 2: Medical imaging (WP15) [\[UC2\]](#)
- Use case 4: Text anonymization on sensitive data (WP17) [\[UC4\]](#)
- Use case 5: Demography (WP18) [\[UC5\]](#)

2.3. SIESTA SERVICE ARCHITECTURE

The first iteration for the SIESTA architecture was elaborated in [\[D6.1\]](#) and it is being updated in WP8, to be reported in D8.1. The following Figures ([FIG1](#), [FIG2](#), [FIG3](#)) depict the high level services.

The versions of the diagrams shown here are simplified for easier reading, you will find the full versions linked in the [bibliography](#), which contain more details and are easier to zoom in.

Figure 1. System landscape (full version [\[F1F1\]](#))

Figure 2. Common services used by the platform (full version [\[FIF2\]](#))

Figure 3. Secure Compute components (full version [\[FIF3\]](#))

2.4. COMMON TERMINOLOGY / SIESTA & RELATED PROJECTS COMMONS

Some existing initiatives, like the International Data Spaces Association with its terminology [\[IDSA\]](#), have endeavoured to create a common vocabulary for the TREs and related projects. This is an interesting step given the diversity of scopes and implementations in this area.

Regarding other actions under the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06 [\[HOIN\]](#) call for proposals, EOSC-ENTRUST has picked the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (“DARE UK Blueprint”) [\[DARE\]](#) as a potential basis for the ENTRUST Blueprint, and they have mapped it to their existing TREs to test its compatibility, and the possible gaps. While DARE UK doesn’t set any requirements regarding specific TREs implementations, it assumes TREs will follow a common minimal standard like the ones in [\[SATRE\]](#) or the ISO 27001.

The ENTRUST Blueprint has been elaborated in parallel with our initial architecture document, therefore in order to check the possible commonalities and divergences with EOSC-ENTRUST we will also map in D8.1 the SIESTA platform to the DARE UK Blueprint or the ENTRUST Blueprint when ready.

A preliminary analysis show some commonalities:

- **SIESTA Personas** can be mapped to the *roles* defined in the DARE UK or Blueprint:
 - The **data rights holder** persona corresponds to DARE's *data controllers* and potentially in some cases to the *data custodians*. However, the *member of the public* role (also in the DARE UK *Data Providers* group) is not present directly in the SIESTA project.
 - The **data user** persona corresponds to the roles in the *Data Consumers* group: *academic researcher* and *commercial researcher*.
 - The **SIESTA platform operator** persona encompasses two of the roles included in the DARE UK Connectors group: the *TRE operators* and the *federation service operators*. However, the mapping of the other roles defined in that group (*information governance professionals*, *indexers* and *linkers*, and *data managers*) are not easy to map to the SIESTA personas.
- In SIESTA the DARE UK *Research Analytics zones* can be identified with the **Interactive Analytics** components see [Fig. 3](#).
- Correspondingly, DARE UK *Secure Data zones* can be mapped to SIESTA's **Secure Storage** components.

- Finally, DARE UK *Query Management zones* are not so easy to map directly to a SIESTA component, but their functionality could be provisioned by a combination of them, and other existing EOSC services.

2.5. EOSC EU-NODE

In line with the INFRAEOSC projects, and as a means to maximize the project outreach, impact and sustainability, the SIESTA project aims to establish as many connections and integrations as possible with the EOSC EU Node. This will ensure a smooth platform integration within the EOSC ecosystem, avoiding redundant development of existing components, and actively contributing to the build-up phases of the EOSC federation, and the implementation of its Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).

FAIR principles and open standards promoted by EOSC will be strictly adhered to. Our focus is on technical interoperability, achieved through the use of open and well-documented APIs, open data formats (e.g. CSV, JSON), standard protocols (OpenID Connect, REST API, ...), and Open Source components. One of the key objectives of the SIESTA platform is to ensure the seamless integration of services within the EOSC federated environment, in alignment with the EOSC Interoperability Framework. Given the focus of the SIESTA project on security and trust in digital systems, special attention will be given to security tools offered by the EOSC ecosystem, and in particular to the federated identity management systems.

All integrated components are fully documented and made publicly accessible. The SIESTA platform will also explore the possibility of registering these services in the EOSC Resource Hub (currently in read only mode) or in the services that are expected to be delivered by the EOSC Beyond project [\[EOSB\]](#), in order to increase their visibility, accessibility, and reusability across the EOSC federation. This will be facilitated by the fact that several stakeholders have already offered services through the previous version of the EOSC marketplace. However, progress on this point is currently constrained by the fact that the onboarding policy of new services is currently a work in progress.

3. GENERAL ARCHITECTURE

Herein proposed architecture is grounded in core principles of secure authentication, fine-grained authorization, resilient networking, and secure computing. Inspired by the broader Zero Trust security model [ZETR], our design assumes no implicit trust—whether inside or outside the network perimeter.

Instead, we enforce continuous verification of identity, strict access controls based on least privilege, and secure, observable communication across all components. This approach enables a flexible yet robust foundation for building and operating secure, cloud-native systems.

The SIESTA platform has high security requirements, so isolation between the different use cases, both current and future ones, is achieved with the use of separate tenants for each use case, so that resources, services and permission rulesets stay separated and easily auditable.

The general architecture of the SIESTA platform is depicted in Figure 4, further technical details are described in depth in the following subchapters.

Figure 4. SIESTA general architecture.

3.1. SECURE COMPUTING

3.1.1. Secure Virtual Machines

OpenStack [\[OPST\]](#) is the leading open-source technology stack for cloud computing platform management, widely deployed across numerous institutions and commercial providers.

The resource providers from the SIESTA project already offer cloud computing resources managed by OpenStack. There are differences in the optional services from site to site, but the base functionality (IaaS) is available in all of them.

Achieving Secure Virtual Machines to provide Confidential Computing resources is challenging, as the technologies involved are very recent and therefore not yet fully integrated into all versions of the relevant operating systems. One of those complex requirements to achieve Confidential Computing, is the newest CPU technologies [\[AMDS\]](#) and the associated software stack updates (kernel drivers, OpenStack version). It will be necessary to migrate production infrastructures to the latest versions of the Linux kernel and OpenStack. This migration cannot always be carried out within a limited timeframe for all systems in production, in order to avoid unavailability or side effects (API changes, hardware no longer supported, etc.). Therefore, some SIESTA cloud providers (CSIC-IFCA, CNRS-IPHC, UISAV) have therefore decided to set up a pilot infrastructure, which prefigures the future production system.

3.1.2. Secure Containers (CoCo)

Secure Containers, often referred to as Confidential Containers (CoCo), represent a lightweight alternative to Secure Virtual Machines for enabling Confidential Computing capabilities in cloud-native environments. While traditional container runtimes provide only process-level isolation through namespaces and control groups (cgroups), CoCo leverages hardware-backed Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) to run containerized workloads in a fully isolated memory space, ensuring that the data and code are protected even from privileged system software, such as the host kernel or hypervisor.

When talking about a lightweight alternative, a clarification has to be made regarding Confidential Containers: they are not containers per se, but at present, support is provided through the creation of an encrypted micro virtual machine that runs a single process inside, which is the “container” that we want to run, thereby providing this “container” with the confidential computing capabilities.

Over the past decade, major CPU vendors have introduced extensions to support these TEEs such as Intel Trust Domain Extensions (TDX) or AMD SEV-SNP (the technology currently available in SIESTA cloud providers), that enable encrypting the virtual machine memory using a unique key per instance.

The use of micro virtual machines to emulate typical containers arises from the situation where most workloads nowadays tend to be containerized and thus Kubernetes, the de-facto container orchestration tool, is used to ensure a reliable and easy-to-scale cluster to execute the different workloads this project requires.

One major constraint when using Confidential Containers is that nested virtualization is not yet supported, which requires the use of bare metal instances. This constraint, combined with the fact that two teams were exploring different approaches to integrate Confidential Containers, led to the creation of two independent Kubernetes clusters. This setup enabled parallel progress and reduced integration bottlenecks, while an open line of communication was maintained between the teams to reinforce collaboration.

Firstly, a hybrid Kubernetes cluster has been deployed on the CSIC-IFCA infrastructure to support both standard and confidential workloads. This cluster includes bare-metal nodes equipped with AMD SEV, specifically dedicated to Confidential Computing, and a set of additional worker nodes running as virtual machines under OpenStack for handling regular workloads. This separation allows the infrastructure to support confidential workloads without compromising the flexibility and scalability of the cloud environment.

This hybrid cluster is created using Kubespray [\[KUBS\]](#), which is a tool that combines Terraform [\[TEFO\]](#) and Ansible [\[ANSI\]](#) to provide infrastructure as code and configure all the needed software for deploying a production ready Kubernetes cluster respectively.

The confidential workloads are run using Kata Containers as the runtime environment, based on containerd, and orchestrated through the CoCo Operator. The CoCo Operator simplifies the management of confidential workloads by automating the configuration of runtime classes, handling node selection for SEV-enabled nodes, and ensuring integration with Kubernetes scheduling policies.

Secondly, a bare metal cluster was deployed on the CSIC-IFCA infrastructure, using scripts developed in-house. As in the first cluster, confidential workloads are run using Kata Containers as the runtime environment, based on containerd, and orchestrated through the CoCo Operator. In addition, a Confidential Containers Key Broker Service (KBS), which facilitates remote attestation-based identity authentication and authorization, secret resource storage and access control was deployed into this cluster.

3.2. AUTHENTICATION

Authentication across the platform is managed through Keycloak [\[KECL\]](#), an open-source identity and access management solution that is deployed self-contained within

the platform itself. Keycloak provides centralized authentication services for both users and applications, supporting standard protocols such as OpenID Connect [\[OIDC\]](#) and SAML. Its integration within the cluster enables seamless single sign-on (SSO) across internal services and dashboards, while also enforcing fine-grained access control based on roles and groups. The deployment is configured for high availability and integrates with external identity providers such as other Keycloak systems (e.g. IFCA one) Github and Google. The next step, once we have defined the fine-grained access policies in the next implementation phase, will be to include EOSC-level authentication via MyAccessID [\[MAID\]](#), providing access to researchers with their institutional credentials via eduGAIN.

In order to deploy and configure Keycloak in the Kubernetes cluster, a GitOps approach is used based on FluxCD [\[FLCD\]](#) and Helm charts. By relying on these tools, it's possible to keep a versioned control of what is deployed in the cluster and to provide an automated way of deploying new changes by just pushing a commit to the corresponding git repository [\[SDEP\]](#).

3.3. USER MANAGEMENT & ACCESS CONTROL

User management and authorization have been implemented via the Keycloak system, following a role-based access control (RBAC) mechanism. For the time being, data rights holders and data users are onboarded manually by the service administrators, allowing them to link with external identities and social identity providers only if they are registered.

Users are part of a given group that is then granted a set of roles, allowing those users in the group to perform certain actions. In the future, users coming from federated identity providers (such as MyAccessID) will be included in different sets of groups, resulting in different roles, but this mapping is yet to be defined by the SIESTA platform operators. Once this initial configuration is performed, the SIESTA platform operators would be able to grant permissions to the different user groups via the RBAC mechanism.

Moreover, this RBAC system will be the basis to enforce different policies on the resources at the different components of the platform. A policy for anonymous remote access may be provided for use cases where this is required. Roles are included in the OpenID Connect access tokens issued by Keycloak and are also accessible via the user info endpoint, enabling downstream services to apply fine-grained authorization policies consistently based on these centrally managed identities. These will be enforced directly at the service level - whether in Harbor [\[HARB\]](#), Kubernetes, or other platform services.

3.3.1. Kubernetes Access Control

For the Kubernetes cluster, the project's access control strategy is built around native mechanisms such as RBACs and enhanced by policy-based governance through **Open Policy Agent [OPAG]**, this component being delivered later by WP12. This approach enables declarative, auditable, and fine-grained access control tailored to multi-tenant, confidential computing environments, and enforced consistently throughout the entire system lifecycle—from configuration and deployment to runtime operation.

Each registered user is mapped to a Kubernetes identity (via OIDC-based tokens) and assigned a set of initial roles that will define the namespaces and quota constraints based on their project affiliation.

Access to Kubernetes resources is scoped using:

- **Namespaces** to enforce logical isolation between users, groups, or use cases.
- **Kubernetes RBAC** for controlling access to cluster-level and namespace-level objects
- **Service Accounts** for managing automated workflows or job execution privileges

Kubernetes RBAC is employed as the first layer of access control inside the cluster, leveraging Role and ClusterRole bindings to define which API groups, resources, and verbs (actions like get, list, update, delete, etc) each user or group can invoke. Namespace isolation ensures that workloads and configurations belonging to one tenant are inaccessible to others by default. Additionally, custom service accounts can be set with different levels of privileges that will be exclusively used by approved external software or scripts.

These RBAC rules match with roles that are managed on Keycloak by using groups that are shown as client scopes when a user requests the ID and Access Token and are verified by both Kubernetes and Keycloak.

3.4. UI/UX-LEVEL

In this chapter we look at the different ways the platform can be accessed by the users (data users or data rights holders) for computing. Depending on the task at hand and its requirements, different access mechanisms are available, all subject to the permissions the authenticated people are granted.

3.4.1. Web application

A web application is required to serve as an interface between the Kubernetes cluster and the users, enabling them to deploy their own services within the secure computing environment. Among the different technologies available for this purpose, Onyxia [\[ONYX\]](#) was selected due to its open-source nature and high degree of customizability, making it an ideal foundation for building the required platform.

Onyxia is a platform designed to provide users with on-demand access to isolated and secure computing environments within a Kubernetes cluster. It simplifies the deployment of personal workspaces and services through a user-friendly web interface, allowing non-expert users to launch compute instances and custom services without direct interaction with the infrastructure components, Kubernetes in this case.

It is structured around a web-based frontend and a backend API layer. The frontend, implemented as a single-page application (SPA) using React, provides users with an intuitive interface to configure and launch services. User requests are processed by the backend, which communicates directly with the Kubernetes cluster. This architecture ensures that each user operates within its own isolated environment, maintaining strict resource and security boundaries.

Additionally, Onyxia integrates with external services such as our Keycloak identity management instance. In the future, it could also be integrated with other services, such as S3-compatible object storage providers, allowing users to upload, download and delete files within their personal buckets. The aspects related to the storage frontend will be detailed in the following chapter ([3.4.2.](#)).

In Onyxia, services are structured into catalogs, where each catalog is backed by a Helm repository. These repositories host multiple Helm charts, with each chart defining the deployment specifications for an individual service.

A test instance has already been deployed to validate the setup before integrating it with the Kubernetes cluster. It is accessible at [\[SCDB\]](#), a screenshot is provided below, in [figure 5](#).

Figure 5. SIESTA project portal page.

With that in mind, the remaining tasks to be addressed for the next iteration of the project include the following:

For the current Onyxia deployment, different settings defining visual aspects, authentication configurations, and Kubernetes deployment options (such as the type of node it runs on) are managed by overriding the values of Onyxia's Helm chart.

However, the goal is to create our own catalog containing the services required for the use cases. In addition, further effort for customizing and adapting the web to the SIESTA project will be required (e.g. branding, adding useful links and documentation). Once the integration with Keycloak is completed, users will be able to log in the application with their credentials and check those catalogs and their respective services.

Apart from that, for now the services launched from the application are set up to run on virtual machines, as deployments on the secure bare-metal nodes are still not available. Thus, the next steps involve integrating the web application with the secure nodes.

[3.4.2. Web-based file sync & share](#)

In order to cope with simple basic file transfers by data rights holders and data users, the chosen solution is to have a Nextcloud solution, that offers a web-based front end to data rights holders and data users of the platform, see [figure 6](#). It is a well-established technology, that counts hundreds of thousands of instances worldwide and that provides hardening and security guidance. It is also the technology that has been chosen by the EOSC EU-Node to provide file sync & share services [\[EOFS\]](#).

Figure 6. Nextcloud Dashboard page.

The core functionalities of Nextcloud meet all basic user needs, without requiring more complex technologies that, for example, depend on command-line expertise, see [figure 7](#). Access to the service is facilitated by the wide range of Nextcloud clients – from the fully featured desktop application to mobile apps available on various app stores, as well as a straightforward web-based interface.

Figure 7. Nextcloud Files browser.

As it is deployed by many universities and research centres, this software is already well-known both by users and system administrators. It is well scrutinized by security teams, and it is interoperable with AAI solutions through its OpenID authentication integration.

Finally, although Nextcloud was chosen right now, it is worth noting the possibility of using Onyxia as a S3-compatible storage front-end, which may be of relevance for specific use cases in the future.

[3.4.3. Interactive analysis](#)

Interactive analysis will be provided to the data user by making Linux applications and full Linux desktops available via the ThinLinc remote desktop solution [\[THLI\]](#). Applications and desktops will be provided on top of Secure Virtual Machines. This capability will provide users with an interactive environment where they can run domain-specific applications and also perform complex workflows.

By restricting data users to utilize remote desktops, we are able to implement more stringent security policies, depending on the data sensitivity. For instance, in the most restrictive case, we can prevent file uploads and downloads, ensuring that sensitive data remains within the secure environment. Additionally, we can disable the clipboard functionality, preventing users from copying and pasting content between the remote desktop and local machines. This significantly reduces the risk of data leakage.

Moreover, ThinLinc remote desktop tunnels all configurations through SSH connections, enhancing security by encrypting the data transmitted between the client and the server. This ensures that all communications are protected from eavesdropping and tampering. Furthermore, ThinLinc supports multi-factor authentication (MFA), adding an extra layer of security by requiring users to provide additional verification beyond just a password.

[3.4.4. Automation API](#)

Besides interactive access by users or data right holders, SIESTA aims to provide efficient platform usage in case there are significant computing needs, so that automation can be implemented via task offloading.

In this regard, automation will be provided to the users by a command line tool, which will follow the structure and capabilities of the various REST APIs available for the users. This command line tool will act as another REST API client, and will take inputs and commands from both the command line, a configuration file(s) and/or input files. The main principle of the command line tool's functionality will be to be as similar to the actual REST API as possible so as not to force users to get acquainted with several different methods and logical ways of controlling the system.

[3.4.5. Bulk data transfer](#)

Based on secure networking best practices (see [chapter 3.6.](#)), any end-to-end encrypted (or securely tunnel-able) bulk data transfer technology can be used as an alternative to the graphical Nextcloud interface.

Depending on the use cases' needs and already implemented data stores, the diversity of available solutions is quite large. For massive data or massively parallelized, data transfer tools can be used such as:

- [SCP](#)
- [Wget](#)
- [Aria2](#)
- [Rsync](#)
- [Rclone](#)
- [AWS S3](#)
- [WebDAV](#)
- [iRODS client](#)
- [OSF client](#) (from Open Science Framework [\[OSFR\]](#))

The choice of the bulk data transfer solution, both the technical implementation and the reasons for the choice, is detailed in each use cases' documentation ([\[UC1\]](#), [\[UC2\]](#), [\[UC4\]](#), [\[UC5\]](#)).

3.5. SECURE STORAGE

3.5.1. Secure Storage challenges

Providing a zero-trust [\[ZETR\]](#) secure storage facility (i.e. without trusting the diverse SIESTA platform operator teams that manage the underlying infrastructure) is a challenging task. The data is encrypted during transfers, but must also remain encrypted at rest and during its usage phase (e.g. data analysis).

The SIESTA platform operators managing the technical infrastructure at provider sites have unlimited privileges on the hardware and running operating systems, so they could access and modify many elements of the system without the end user noticing. However, in accordance with the goals of SIESTA, the platform operators should not have access at any moment to an unencrypted version of the sensitive data, nor have access to any encryption keys used for that purpose. So, one of the challenges is to find a way to manage both encryption and the storage of the keys to offer a trustworthy solution.

The section below describes the different levels where we can provide encryption technology, and for each of them the advantages and main drawbacks. It goes down the levels from the service level (like data transfer) to the bare storage system, by passing through the cloud level (CC VMs or containers) :

- Data transfer (in-transit) encryption: this type of encryption is essential when transferring data over the network, but is not enough on its own. While data is protected during transmission, it is not secured at rest - whether on the source, the destination, or any intermediate steps.
- Storage-level (at-rest) encryption: the security at this level depends on who controls the encryption keys. If the keys are managed by the storage

administrator rather than by the user, then the administrator may also have access to the data. This solution, which is often offered by cloud operators, cannot be considered secure for the purposes of the SIESTA project. Encryption keys need to be managed directly by the data rights holder to ensure data confidentiality.

- Virtual Machine block storage volume-level encryption: since the data rights holders (or their delegates, see [2.2](#)) are the only ones in charge of this encryption, it offers the safest way to protect data on storage. Only data rights holders are authorized to mount the encrypted volume and decrypt its contents. In consequence, data is unencrypted only inside the virtual environments. This solution is truly secure only when running within the TEE (VMs or containers), but not for the operating system image used to instantiate the secure environment. Operating system images must therefore remain stateless, especially regarding secrets used for data encryption and decryption. On the other hand, access by data users is handled by different services that are set up above this storage, and this is where the permissions are enforced. Data users never have any access to the low-level storage and encryption layer.

As Virtual Machine block storage volume-level encryption is the most robust solution, the SIESTA platform secure storage is based on it. This solution requires that the secrets' usage inside the TEE must be bootstrapped from an external source. Encryption keys need to be provided securely by the data rights holders after the TEE has started (i.e. post-boot). This is because the TEE's encrypted memory is only fully secure once the operating system is running in multi-user mode. The main drawback of this solution is that it requires data rights holders to interact with the TEEs, at each time the environment is (re-)booted. However, this small inconvenience is counterbalanced by the strong security assurance that data remains properly protected and not accessible to unauthorized users.

In all cases, another important consideration is that secrets injected in the running VMs must never leak from the VM's encrypted memory under any circumstances.

[3.5.2. Secure Storage architecture](#)

To ensure easy deployments and seamless technology reuse, the SIESTA platform's secure storage component was designed with a modular, layered approach. This enables the project to use diverse front-ends or change some parts without affecting the other stakeholders, being from the SIESTA platform operator team or data rights holders & users from the use cases. The layered architecture introduced in the following chapters, is described visually in [figure 8](#) below.

Figure 8. Secure Storage architecture

The different layers and modules are the following:

- A storage **backend** layer (see [3.5.3.](#)) that handles the diverse low-level cloud storage technologies and adds encryption above that in a secure way. This level is not directly accessible by anyone, it is set up **on behalf** of the data rights holder in an **automated** way. This is where the sensitive data is held securely. This can only be accessed through the services in the frontend layer, described below.
- A **frontend** layer that is composed of a set of different services for the data rights holders and data users to access data sets according to their respective permissions. These services, as parts of the [3.4. UI/UX](#), present the data rights holders and data users with different interfaces that are easy to work with, or that are suited to massive data transfers. For example a web-based content collaboration platform (something like google drive, Nextcloud [\[NXTC\]](#), see [3.4.2.](#), etc.), and in addition to that, other file transfer technologies more suited to bulk data management like f.e. Rsync [\[RSYN\]](#), see [3.4.5.](#) The services provided at this level can be tailored for the different use cases needs, and allows the SIESTA platform to be used by people that are accustomed to command-line interfaces, or who prefer an interactive graphical user experience. Each use case can choose the set of services best fulfilling its needs.

In addition, to address as fully as possible the needs expressed by the use cases in terms of secure storage requirements, the following actions have been undertaken:

- Several bulk data transfer solutions have been tested to identify those that can be seamlessly integrated into the workflows of the use cases. This is particularly valuable for massive data ingestion tasks, where manual processing would be impractical. It significantly improves both the performance and reliability of the overall system.
- A data lake solution, based on iRODS [\[IROD\]](#) technology, has been deployed to provide a comprehensive service for the needing use cases that do not already have one. Further details in section [3.5.6.](#)

[3.5.3. Secure Storage backend](#)

For the secure storage backend, the chosen solution is to use standard, out-of-the box storage provided by the cloud computing software stacks. A software-based secure encryption layer is added above the storage backend.

Cloud storage is made available as virtual block storage volumes to virtual machines. For containers, a cloud provider plugin maps these volumes as defined by the Kubernetes cluster definition, creating an automatic environment of dynamically provided volumes for containers.

The cloud storage is provided to the secured virtual machine or container, upon which a secure encryption layer is stacked. With the encryption and associated secrets usage

being made at the operating system level, from inside the trusted execution environment (TEE), they can be fully trusted, as it is ensured that SIESTA platform operators cannot have access to unencrypted data or decryption keys.

The encryption layer consumes a block device from the layer below and provides a (virtual) block device to the layers above. This is where a standard POSIX filesystem is set up, which then can be mounted from the operating system.

For OpenStack-based cloud platforms, the cinder on-demand volume service provides the virtual machines with virtual block device volumes, which can be backed by different concrete storage technologies (ceph, iSCSI, etc.).

The block device encryption is provided by the Linux kernel's LUKS subsystem which is the de-facto standard of software-based block storage encryption within the Linux ecosystem. As an ubiquitous solution well integrated into the Linux kernel, it is scrutinized by many security experts across the industry and by academic researchers in computer security.

The file system used in the last layer of the secure storage backend can be any of the ones provided by the Linux kernel, the main ones being EXT4 and XFS. The SIESTA project advises to stay with one of those two, as they have since long proven their reliability and robustness. Ansible-based automated deployment solution [\[SSSA\]](#) provided by the SIESTA project allows users to choose whichever is the most suitable one for the use case deployment.

[3.5.4. Secrets management](#)

As seen above in [3.5.1](#), secrets must reside on the data rights holders side, but even there, they must be properly secured. The chosen solution to deploy the secure storage software stack & configuration is Ansible [\[ANSI\]](#), so the secrets are stored in Ansible encrypted vault files. The responsibility to share these files and the associated decryption keys are fully devoted to the data rights holders (or their delegates). No one else should be given access to them.

When those secrets are inserted into the running TEE, they are used to set up the data volumes software (de-)encryption, and should only reside there for as long as needed and not more than that. Additionally, to ensure that the data remains strictly within the TEE, secrets should never be stored on any kind of persistent storage. Instead, they reside in a small temporary filesystem backed exclusively by encrypted memory (an unswappable Linux tmpfs), which guarantees that secrets and data stay confined within the TEE.

If the encryption keys are stored in a secrets management system (an SMS, like the OpenStack Barbican module or an HashiCorp Vault), the same kind of issue as in the above paragraph is present: access to this secrets management system need a secret on its own, which needs to be provided to the TEE. We're back to square one: the TEE cannot **retain** those credentials or tokens required to access that SMS, it has to be given

from the data rights holders (or their delegates). Therefore, the necessary access information must be securely provided to the TEE after it has fully initialized and entered its secure execution mode.

[3.5.5. Data Lifecycle management](#)

For the first platform release of the SIESTA platform, we can already use the usual mechanisms for task automation to handle data lifecycle requirements. Because different needs may arise during the lifetime of the data, the agile solution is to use different tools with specific capabilities that can be easily combined to achieve the desired functionality.

Because a simple ad-hoc combination of small, orthogonal tools may not be sufficient to support advanced data lifecycle management scenarios, services with enhanced functionalities need to be provided to the use cases. These capabilities are available in a few specialized software stacks, including certain data lake (DL) solutions. Since the SIESTA platform was already intended to offer a DL solution, it was decided to adopt that DL solution for data lifecycle management (see [3.5.6.](#)).

[3.5.6. Secure DataLake](#)

For use cases that require advanced data lifecycle management, data lake technologies can significantly enhance the capabilities available to the most demanding projects. Within the SIESTA project, an iRODS-based approach has been deployed, leveraging the expertise of the CNRS partner. CNRS has been developing and managing an iRODS production service for the France Grilles research infrastructure since 2014, ensuring a robust and reliable solution.

The primary aim of this data lake deployment is to provide use cases with a platform to test and evaluate this advanced solution. To ensure timely availability, the initial version of this service integrates within the secure virtual machine and secure storage services of SIESTA. For use cases interested in leveraging this service, dedicated iRODS instances will be deployed in WP9. Each instance will be isolated from the others through network segregation and data encryption, ensuring a secure environment for all users. Additionally, iRODS' support for OpenID and flexible auditing through specific rules allows for seamless integration with the SIESTA authentication and auditing services.

iRODS supports several critical security features, including fine-grained access control, encryption both client-side, at rest and in transit, and comprehensive auditing capabilities for data access. These features enable the level of security required by the SIESTA project. Looking ahead, the next steps involve further enhancements to the deployment by connecting to SIESTA services (authentication, auditing) and optimizing the automatic deployment of the iRODS instances. The service will be further tailored to use cases' needs following WP8's input.

3.6. SECURE NETWORKING

To ensure data security, integrity and confidentiality during its transfers in and out of the SIESTA platform we have ensured that all communications in the platform remain properly ciphered, implemented using proven protocols and secure networking recipes such as:

- HTTPS for all API communications.
- SSH (and scp) with public key encryption for connections to remote desktops.

Furthermore, the security hardening work package (WP12) will leverage Cilium's eBPF capabilities and advanced network policies to achieve fine-grained workload isolation at runtime.

Security assessments for this important part of the platform will be handled from multiple points of view during the second half of the project. Security audits will ensure the implemented solutions are up to current standards. Monitoring will ensure real-time detection of security problems. Tamper-proof logging facilities will help with any forensics in case a security breach is detected and will be further explored in the work package WP12.

3.7. DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT

3.7.1. Code repository

A code repository offers a storage system designed to manage source code as well as other assets related to software development. The main task of a code repository is code versioning, which is essential to keep track of the changes made to a codebase over time, especially in a collaborative development environment.

For this purpose Gitlab is used by the SIESTA platform developers and operators, in a self hosted instance at IFCA. Gitlab is a well-known and mature open-source platform that provides not only a git repository but also very powerful DevSecOps capabilities with its integrated pipelines.

Given the nature of the project, where confidentiality is paramount, a self hosted Gitlab instance offers more control and privacy compared to using other platforms such as Github or Bitbucket even when using private projects as they are subject to changes in their privacy policy and therefore could, for example, start using code from private repositories to train their LLMs.

The Gitlab instance [\[IFGI\]](#) can be accessed by using the IFCA SSO login service, meaning that all registered users can enter, but the elements they have access to is limited depending on the affiliation they have within the project.

3.7.2. Container image registry

A container registry is a collection of repositories made to store container images. A container image is a file that can be composed of multiple layers which can execute

applications in a single container instance as an isolated runtime environment. Container images form the backbone of modern cloud-native applications, encapsulating all dependencies and runtime environments needed to execute software reliably. However, these images can also become vectors for vulnerabilities, misconfigurations, and malicious code if not properly curated.

In the SIESTA platform, we are utilizing Harbor [\[HARB\]](#) – a Cloud Native Computing Foundation [\[CNCF\]](#) project– which offers a powerful, self-hosted container image registry built specifically to meet these needs. Unlike public registries such as Docker Hub, Harbor is engineered with a strong emphasis on secure computing, compliance, and operational sovereignty. It stands out as a critical tool for organizations and projects like SIESTA that demand full control over their software supply chain.

Harbor addresses the risk for vulnerabilities by embedding security into every stage of the container lifecycle –build, store, deploy. By self-hosting Harbor, we strengthen our control over the container images, reducing reliance on third-party services and mitigating the risks associated with data exfiltration, unauthorized access, or service outages. Harbor supports robust access control, end-to-end image provenance, and continuous security assessments, making it ideal for regulated environments or for confidential computing scenarios like ours.

The following are the key features of Harbor, with all to be configured after WP12 security hardening completion, and with vulnerability scan being enabled in this release:

- **Image Signing and Provenance Verification**
 - Harbor integrates with Cosign to allow content signing and image validation. This ensures that only verified and trusted images are promoted or deployed. Image signing protects against tampering by verifying that images have not been modified since they were signed by a trusted authority. This chain of trust is essential for compliance with modern software supply chain security standards like SLSA (Supply-chain Levels for Software Artifacts).
- **Trivy-Powered Vulnerability Scanning**
 - A standout feature of Harbor is its built-in support for Trivy [\[TRIV\]](#), an open-source vulnerability scanner. Trivy scans container images for known vulnerabilities (CVEs) across OS packages and language-specific dependencies. These scans can be automated during image push, ensuring that unscanned or vulnerable images never enter production. Harbor’s UI and API provide detailed vulnerability reports, severity breakdowns, and remediation guidance—empowering teams to shift security left in their development process.
- **SBOM Generation (Software Bill of Materials)**
 - As part of a secure SDLC (Software Development Lifecycle), Harbor can generate and store SBOMs (Software Bills of Materials) for container

images. An SBOM offers a comprehensive inventory of components within an image, enabling transparency and traceability. This is vital for zero-trust architectures and regulatory compliance, such as the EU Cyber Resilience Act and the European Union’s Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA). These regulations increasingly demand visibility into software components, secure software development practices, and accountability across the supply chain.

- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Identity Integration**
 - Harbor supports fine-grained RBAC and integrates seamlessly with enterprise identity providers such as LDAP, Active Directory, and OIDC. Users can be assigned roles scoped to projects, ensuring that only authorized personnel can push, pull, or modify images. This is particularly useful in multi-tenant environments or organizations with strict separation-of-duties policies.
- **Image Replication and Disaster Recovery**
 - Harbor supports bi-directional image replication across multiple registry instances—on-premises or across cloud environments. This facilitates geo-distributed development teams, improves availability, and provides redundancy in case of system failure or breach.

The following [figure 9](#), is an example of a freshly scanned container image of an alpine operating system, with a couple of medium severity level vulnerabilities discovered.

Figure 9. Example: harbor-scanned container image.

The noncompliant container image, with minimal vulnerability severity level defined in Harbor project configuration, will not be permitted to be pulled from the registry - resulting in proactive security risk mitigation. The default recommended severity level allowance will be specified in WP12, but the Use Case partners may override it based on their specific needs.

3.8. SECURE MONITORING AND AUDITING

A platform such as SIESTA must ensure that access to its resources is performed in a secure and private manner. This requires that each user role is governed by well-defined access control policies that restrict access to data and computational resources based on the principle of least privilege. Moreover, all services and software libraries comprising the system must be regularly updated or, when updates are not immediately feasible, properly mitigated against known vulnerabilities. This serves as a key for ensuring the integrity, confidentiality, and traceability of operational and security events is essential.

This matter is done using continuous monitoring tools such as Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS), which monitor traffic for suspicious activity, and Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems (HIDS), which oversee the behavior of individual hosts, particularly those running private and sensitive data. These systems rely on rule-based configurations to identify anomalies and automatically notify system administrators when any predefined critical threshold is exceeded.

For the SIESTA platform, **OSSEC**-based (Open Source HIDS SECURITY) [\[OSSE\]](#) monitoring solutions have been deployed to track the status of each node within the Kubernetes cluster, along with the services running within that environment.

Among the OSSEC implementations, Wazuh [\[WAZU\]](#) stands out as one of the most powerful and widely adopted solutions. It offers a comprehensive suite of features including log analysis, file integrity monitoring, rootkit detection, and real-time alerting. Wazuh enables the observation of both the physical machines hosting the Kubernetes cluster and the worker nodes, which are implemented as virtual instances in the SIESTA cloud providers.

In this first release of the platform, Kubernetes is installed on physical nodes used for conducting all Confidential Computing (CoCo) testing. This setup makes the initial deployment of Wazuh relatively straightforward, allowing for focused validation of security mechanisms and anomaly detection in a controlled environment. Moreover, an initial setup for connecting Wazuh with the containers managed by Kubernetes is in progress.

[Figure 10](#) illustrates an example of the Wazuh dashboard, displaying the number of successful and denied login attempts recorded on one of the physical nodes running Kubernetes. This information provides immediate visibility into potential unauthorized access attempts and supports proactive incident response.

Figure 10. Wazuh dashboard example for login attempts to one of the K8s SIESTA platform

This initial setup allows us to extend it towards the recording of actions performed in the platform. The next step, to be implemented in the next period, is to ensure that this information can be provided in a verifiable and tamper-proof way.

In order to do so, we plan to deploy an **auditing** infrastructure as a fundamental component that provides a detailed and verifiable record of user actions, system changes, and access to sensitive resources. These audit logs play a key role in incident response, compliance verification, and long-term system accountability.

To tackle the auditing task, we have leveraged the Wazuh log collection and analysis capabilities to gather system logs, which are then forwarded to the next layer: the tamper-proofing component. This initial step is straightforward in Wazuh, as it incorporates a log analysis engine that supports a wide range of formats including system journals, syslogs, and security logs such as the usual “auth.log” and “secure” files, and enables the detection of anomalous events. The collected logs can be tailored and enriched before being provided to the tamper-proof tool. In the second step, these logs serve as the basis for auditing and tamper-proofing operations, building upon the data retrieved by Wazuh.

For the second component, advanced technologies are being studied to incorporate in the SIESTA platform. **Google Trillian** [GOTR] is an open source software component that provides a cryptographically verifiable append-only log based on Merkle trees, enabling integrity guarantees even in untrusted environments. This way, transparent and variable logging can be used to ensure the integrity of the collected actions.

3.9. DYNAMIC DOMAIN NAME SERVICE

In modern Cloud environments, application and platform services are often deployed dynamically. Typically, these services run on virtual machines and are accessible only through IP addresses or pre-configured hostnames assigned by cloud providers. This approach complicates the assignment of meaningful domain names and often requires

manual configuration by administrators, introducing delays in service deployment and slowing down the service lifecycle.

The SIESTA project addresses this challenge through a dynamic DNS service, enabling fully automated hostname registration and dynamic IP-to-hostname association. Service owners can authenticate via EGI Check-in, register user-friendly, memorable hostnames (e.g., *harbor.cloud.eosc-siesta.eu* for the container registry), and associate them with their servers. This allows users to access services through these custom hostnames without dealing with underlying infrastructure changes.

Dynamic DNS significantly simplifies the deployment and management of services in dynamic cloud infrastructures. It eliminates the complications caused by changing IP addresses at each deployment and facilitates the automatic issuance of SSL certificates for registered hostnames. With this system, service providers can seamlessly migrate applications between local infrastructure and cloud environments—or across different cloud sites—without disrupting user access or requiring manual reconfiguration.

4. USE CASES

WP7 has been thoroughly working with the different use cases' work packages (WP14 to WP18) to ensure that the platform architecture meets their requirements, to onboard them on the platform, and to help them use the provided resources and services. As evidenced by the start of WP8, there's still work to do to make the platform easier to use, and to finalize the other tasks, like the security hardening, for example. The [table 1](#) depicts the use cases' current use of SIESTA services.

	WP14 / UC1 Epidemiology	WP15 / UC2 Medical imaging	WP17 / UC4 Text	WP18 / UC5 Demography
ThinLinc				
Nextcloud				
iRODS				
SSH	X	X		X
SCP	X	X		X
VMs		X		
Containers	X	X		X
Gitlab	X			X
Onyxia	X			X

Secrets Store				
Dynamic DNS				
Integration API	X			

Table 1. Use cases service current use.

Note: WP16 / UC3 (Energy domain) is excluded from this table because of delays in the replacement of the original partner (AlgoWatt) by Predictia.

5. SIESTA INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS

5.1. CSIC / IFCA

After several attempts to make Confidential Containers working above OpenStack, we decided to reserve a couple of AMD SEV-capable physical machines to start working on the secure containers probes. At this state, the Kubernetes cluster is running on top of these machines in order to provide a PoC platform where the authentication system and the rest of the worker nodes serve their resources to test the use cases. In parallel, we are working on the update of OpenStack services to ensure the compatibility with the kernel SEV-SNP feature for running secure environments.

As mentioned in previous sections, the Kubernetes cluster is a hybrid with both VMs provided by OpenStack and the two aforementioned machines. The provisioning of the VMs and the installation of the needed software is done by using Kubespray with all the configuration files and scripts versioned and uploaded to the siesta-kubespray-deployment repository on Gitlab [\[SKUD\]](#).

To enable CoCo under the Kubernetes cluster the latest version of the CoCo Operator is installed (v0.14.0 as the time of writing this document). The operator creates a series of runtimes based on the detected capabilities of the hardware running it -AMD SEV in this case- and downloads, installs and configures the Kata containers components on the designated worker nodes.

This setup was initially tested on Ubuntu 20.04 as it was the latest supported version on OpenStack before the upgrade. After multiple iterations and custom configurations CoCo was successfully enabled in the cluster though with some limitations and trade-offs that finally led to the decision of upgrading OpenStack to a newer version to support Ubuntu 22.04 where CoCo had been successfully tested and was working without these limitations. Such limitations included the need of manually installing Nydus Snapshotter as an external DaemonSet and the need to use a shared file system due to guest image download not working when using AMD SEV among others.

Currently, the platform is able to create both normal and confidential containers that are distributed on the different nodes depending on the nature of the container. Further challenges need to be resolved, such as configuring the Trustee instance to verify the trustworthiness of a confidential container.

5.2. UISAV

We decided to add support for Confidential Computing virtual machines to our production OpenStack cloud infrastructure. We added two dedicated computing nodes with HW support for AMD SEV and AMD SEV-SNP technologies, local project for SIESTA virtual organisation, VM flavors and images necessary to start virtual machines with AMD SEV support. We added integration with SIESTA AAI to allow SIESTA users to start confidential virtual machines at our cloud site. We also allocated resources on regular nodes so users are able to run regular virtual machines if necessary. We also worked on adding support for AMD SEV-SNP (running confidential containers inside virtual machines) but this was not completed yet as the support for AMD SEV-SNP requires recent kernel (v6.11) and Qemu (v9.1) versions which are too new to be in the set of supported versions for our OpenStack version and OS. Future work will also include testing of remote attestation of confidential virtual machines.

5.3. CNRS / IPHC

To address the challenges outlined in Section [3.1.1](#), it has been decided not to modify our production Cloud infrastructure for the initial version of the SIESTA platform. This approach enabled the agile deployment of new experimental services, allowing the integration of cutting-edge technologies to support confidential computing solutions, while also ensuring integration of services already in production. This strategy was further supported by the acquisition of the latest hardware solutions. Based on feedback collected in WP8, some of these services will be integrated into the production environment as part of WP9.

In parallel with the deployment of confidential computing services, we also designed and tested an automated solution for provisioning encrypted secure storage volumes for virtual machines. This provides a robust and reliable basis for developing more advanced storage-related services. A secure storage front-end, based on a web-accessible interface (Nextcloud), has been implemented. For use cases with more functionality needs, a data lake solution based on iRODS has also been deployed and made available.

CNRS worked closely with WP15 to provide them with early access to the necessary resources for implementing their computational pipelines. This early-stage collaboration and feedback permit us to identify issues related to the services they were using. It helped us perform corrective actions and provide fully operational services to the other use-cases. Regular interactions are maintained with the other use cases that do not currently use our services, in order to understand their requirements

and consider alternative solutions. The output of WP8 will also contribute to the development of this infrastructure, and eventually the setting of new services.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The WP7 implemented SIESTA project's services to an extent, which will be perfected within the following work packages. The services available encompass AAI, secure storage, secure containers & virtual machines, web front-end, data transfer, code management, container image registry, dynamic DNS, and secrets storage. The first iteration of those services fulfils basic needs for the use cases, but needs refinements to achieve seamless use. The following work packages will continue to iterate the architecture to advance its readiness level into a production platform.

In addition to enhancements for the offered services to take WP8 feedback into account and refine the platform, we also envisioned a few areas where we can continue to explore what can be provided for greater usability, and interoperability with other EOSC services.

For example, we have implemented a Data lake solution based on iRODS. Other solutions are available and could be of interest, like OneData [\[ONED\]](#). This solution could also provide enhanced features for data storage, and will be assessed. Until now, the data lake solution has not been used by any of the use cases. WP8 will permit us to understand the reason for this and enable us to acquire new users in the future to shape and implement production-ready data lake services.

Our current use cases were reluctant or forbidden by law to put real sensitive data in a PoC platform, this problem should be tackled in future iterations, and trust must be gained from the potential user base. To increase the trust in the SIESTA platform, its security will be examined and assessed by a cybersecurity engineering team, who will be responsible for carrying out in-depth checks, including intrusion tests. This will reinforce a proactive approach to security. The opportunity to integrate these tests into an automation pipeline will also be studied, to ensure continuous and systematic monitoring of the system's robustness.

Finally, the services approved by the use cases in WP8 will be put into production by WP9. This phase involves setting up operational supervision to ensure their availability, performance and security. It also requires close coordination between the technical teams, in order to guarantee constant operation and easy integration into the use case work environments. Deployment, monitoring and maintenance procedures will be established to ensure stable and scalable operation of the services.

Even if a tremendous amount of work has been provided by the SIESTA project, there remains a lot to explore and progress to be made. Confidential Computing is the way forward for cloud resource providers, as already understood and recognized by the private sector. We should make this happen in the public and academic sector too, because the needs are numerous, and current events on the world stage are also giving hints that this trend will not stop soon, if ever.

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